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ANALYSIS OF PATIENT SATISFACTION WITH THE QUALITY OF DENTAL CARE AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR HEALTHCARE ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. Patient satisfaction is one of the key integral indicators of the quality of medical care and the effectiveness of healthcare organizations. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, studies on patient satisfaction with dental care are limited and are mainly represented by local observations, which determines the need for additional research in specific regions of the country.

Objective. To analyze patient satisfaction with the quality of dental care and to identify the main factors influencing patients' subjective assessment of medical services.

Materials and Methods. A cross-sectional sociological study was conducted using a questionnaire survey of 120 patients of a private dental clinic in Shymkent in 2024–2025. Patient satisfaction was assessed using a specially designed questionnaire including indicators of treatment quality, dentist–patient interaction, patient information, waiting time, and appointment availability. Quality parameters were evaluated using a 10-point scale. Statistical analysis was performed using methods of variation statistics with data presented as $M \pm m$ and n (%). Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results. A high level of patient satisfaction with the quality of dental care was identified. The mean overall satisfaction score was 8.7 ± 0.1 points. The highest scores were obtained for treatment quality (9.1 ± 0.1 points) and dentist attitude (9.2 ± 0.1 points). Lower scores were observed for waiting time (8.1 ± 0.2 points) and appointment availability (8.0 ± 0.2 points). A high level of satisfaction (8–10 points) was observed in 76.7% of patients.

Conclusions. Analysis of patient satisfaction makes it possible to identify key areas for improving the performance of a dental clinic and can be considered an effective management tool for healthcare organizations. Regular monitoring of patient satisfaction contributes to improving the quality of dental care.

Keywords: patient satisfaction, quality of dental care, healthcare organization management, quality of medical care, patient survey

Introduction

Under modern conditions of healthcare development, one of the key priorities is improving the quality of medical care and enhancing management mechanisms in healthcare organizations [1]. Particular importance is attached to the study of patient satisfaction, since this indicator reflects not only clinical treatment outcomes but also the effectiveness of healthcare organization, accessibility of services, and the quality of interaction between medical personnel and patients [2]. The study of patient opinions makes it possible to identify problematic aspects of healthcare organizations and to develop managerial decisions aimed at improving their performance. According to Kazakhstani researchers, the analysis of patient satisfaction with various aspects of the diagnostic and treatment

process contributes to strategic decision-making and increases the competitiveness of healthcare organizations under market conditions [3].

Dental care occupies an important place in the system of outpatient medical care for the population [4]. Consideration of dental care within the framework of primary health care emphasizes the importance of service accessibility and patient-centeredness [5]. The high prevalence of dental diseases and the significant rate of patient visits necessitate continuous improvement in the organization of dental services. In the context of the development of the private healthcare sector, the assessment of dental care quality from the patient's perspective becomes increasingly important, since the subjective evaluation of received services largely determines the choice of a medical organization and the level of trust in the healthcare system [6]. Under modern conditions, patient satisfaction is considered one of the indicators of the effectiveness of dental treatment and the organization of dental care [7].

In international practice, patient satisfaction is widely used as an integral indicator of the quality of medical care and the effectiveness of healthcare organizations [8]. Studies show that the level of satisfaction with dental care depends not only on clinical treatment outcomes but also on socio-hygienic factors, the level of patient awareness, and the conditions under which medical care is provided. Thus, according to a study involving 1,386 respondents, a statistically significant relationship was identified between satisfaction with dental care and socio-hygienic living conditions as well as demographic characteristics of patients [9].

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, studies on patient satisfaction with dental care remain limited and are mainly of a local nature. One such study is the work of A.T. Ulmanov and G.K. Sarybayeva (2018), conducted in a private dental clinic in Astana. The study demonstrated that the majority of patients rated the quality of dental care highly, while no unsatisfactory evaluations were reported. The authors established that patient satisfaction was primarily associated with the attitude of medical personnel, treatment outcomes, and the material and technical resources of the clinic [10].

Despite the available studies, the assessment of patient satisfaction with dental care in certain regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan remains insufficiently investigated. In particular, there are no data on the subjective assessment of dental care quality among the population of Southern Kazakhstan, including the city of Shymkent, where the private dental sector is actively developing. Regional features of dental care organization, socio-economic conditions, and patterns of healthcare utilization may significantly influence the level of patient satisfaction, which necessitates further research.

Thus, the analysis of patient satisfaction with the quality of dental care represents an important management tool for healthcare organizations, making it possible to identify problem areas in the organization of medical services and to develop measures for their improvement [11]. Conducting a study of patient satisfaction in a private dental clinic in Shymkent will provide additional data on the quality of dental care and help identify directions for improving the effectiveness of healthcare organization management.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to analyze patient satisfaction with the quality of dental care and to identify the main manageable factors influencing patients' subjective assessment of medical services, using a private dental clinic in the city of Shymkent as an example.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the level of patient satisfaction with the quality of dental care.
2. To assess the main parameters of dental care quality from the patients' perspective (treatment quality, dentist attitude, patient information, waiting time, and appointment availability).
3. To identify the most significant factors influencing overall patient satisfaction.
4. To determine the possibilities of using patient satisfaction analysis as a management tool for healthcare organizations.

Materials and Methods

The study was designed as a cross-sectional sociological survey using questionnaires administered to patients of a private dental clinic in Shymkent.

Organizational aspects of dental care provision were considered in accordance with the current national standard for the organization of dental care in the Republic of Kazakhstan [12].

The study period covered 2024–2025.

A total of 120 patients who received dental care in outpatient conditions were included in the study. Inclusion criteria were seeking dental care and providing informed consent to participate in the survey. Patients aged 18 years and older were included. Exclusion criteria were refusal to participate and incomplete questionnaires.

To assess patient satisfaction, a special questionnaire was developed based on international approaches to the evaluation of healthcare quality and patient satisfaction [13]. The structure of the questionnaire included several sections [14]:

- assessment of treatment quality;
- assessment of dentist and medical staff attitude;
- assessment of waiting time;
- assessment of patient information about treatment;
- assessment of appointment availability;
- overall assessment of satisfaction with medical care [15].

Quality parameters of dental care were evaluated using a 10-point scale, where 1 point indicated minimal satisfaction and 10 points indicated maximal satisfaction [16]. In addition, dichotomous responses (“yes/no”) and categorical ratings (“excellent”, “good”, “satisfactory”) were used.

Statistical processing of the obtained data was performed using methods of variation statistics. Quantitative indicators are presented as mean values with standard error ($M \pm m$). Qualitative indicators are presented as absolute numbers and percentages (n, %).

Parametric statistical methods were used to assess the significance of differences. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

The study was conducted on a voluntary and anonymous basis. All respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and provided consent to participate in the survey.

Results

A total of 120 patients of a private dental clinic in Shymkent who received dental care in 2024–2025 participated in the study.

Among the surveyed patients, 72 were women (60.0%) and 48 were men (40.0%). The mean age of patients was 34.6 ± 1.2 years (Table 1).

The largest proportion of patients belonged to the age group of 25–44 years — 68 individuals (56.7%), corresponding to the most active group of dental service users.

Repeat visits were reported in 68 patients (56.7%), while 52 patients (43.3%) visited the clinic for the first time.

The main reason for seeking dental care was treatment of dental caries and its complications — 58 patients (48.3%). Preventive examinations accounted for 22.5% of visits, prosthodontic treatment for 16.7%, and surgical dentistry for 12.5%.

Table 1 – Characteristics of the study participants (n = 120)

Parameter	n	%
Male	48	40.0
Female	72	60.0
First-time visit	52	43.3
Repeat visit	68	56.7
Therapeutic dentistry	58	48.3
Preventive examination	27	22.5
Prosthodontics	20	16.7

Oral surgery	15	12.5
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Assessment of Dental Care Quality

The analysis showed that the majority of patients positively evaluated the quality of dental care. The highest satisfaction scores were observed for the parameters dentist attitude and treatment quality. The lowest scores were obtained for waiting time and appointment availability (Table 2).

Table 2 – Assessment of Dental Care Quality Parameters (points)

Indicator	M±m
Treatment quality	9.1±0.1
Dentist attitude	9.2±0.1
Patient information	8.8±0.1
Waiting time	8.1±0.2
Appointment availability	8.0±0.2

The mean overall level of patient satisfaction with dental care was 8.7±0.1 points.

A high level of satisfaction (8–10 points) was observed in 92 patients (76.7%).

A moderate level of satisfaction (5–7 points) was observed in 28 patients (23.3%) (Table 3).

No cases of low satisfaction (less than 5 points) were identified.

The obtained data are consistent with the results of a study conducted in a private dental clinic in Astana, where a high level of patient satisfaction with dental care was also reported [4].

When dental care quality was assessed using a categorical scale, most patients rated the quality of services as good or excellent.

Table 3 – Overall Assessment of Dental Care Quality

Rating	Number	%
Excellent	54	45.0
Good	52	43.3
Satisfactory	14	11.7

Most patients (88 individuals, 73.3%) reported that the cost of treatment corresponded to the quality of the provided medical services.

A total of 96 patients (80.0%) indicated their willingness to recommend the clinic to others.

Discussion

The obtained results indicate a high level of patient satisfaction with the quality of dental care in the private dental clinic in Shymkent. The mean overall satisfaction score was **8.7±0.1 points**, and more than three quarters of patients rated the quality of care as high. The absence of low ratings indicates generally favorable patient perceptions of dental care quality and the effectiveness of the treatment process organization.

The highest scores were obtained for the parameters treatment quality and dentist attitude, confirming the leading role of medical staff professionalism and clinical treatment outcomes in the formation of patient satisfaction.

The data obtained by other authors demonstrate that patient satisfaction is closely associated with the attitude of medical personnel and treatment outcomes, which is consistent with the results of the present study [4].

The study showed that relatively lower scores were obtained for waiting time and appointment availability. These indicators mainly reflect organizational aspects of healthcare delivery and represent manageable factors within a healthcare organization. A similar interpretation of results has been reported in studies of patient satisfaction with outpatient care, where patient surveys have been

shown to help identify organizational shortcomings and support improvements in healthcare management.

The obtained results confirm that patient satisfaction is an integral indicator of the effectiveness of healthcare delivery. According to Kazakhstani researchers, the level of patient satisfaction can be considered one of the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of dental treatment and the organization of dental care.

This makes it possible to use the results of patient surveys not only to assess the quality of medical services but also to develop measures aimed at improving the performance of healthcare organizations.

Comparison of the results of the present study with data from international studies demonstrates common patterns in the formation of satisfaction with dental care. Studies involving large population samples show that patient satisfaction depends not only on treatment quality but also on social and organizational factors of healthcare delivery.

In particular, the conditions under which medical care is provided, the accessibility of healthcare services, and the level of patient information about treatment are of considerable importance [17,18].

Thus, the obtained results indicate that a high level of patient satisfaction with dental care is largely determined by the quality of the treatment process and the professional competence of medical staff, whereas the main directions for improving healthcare organization performance include optimization of the appointment scheduling process and reduction of patient waiting time.

The present study confirms the feasibility of using patient satisfaction analysis as a management tool for healthcare organizations [19]. Regular monitoring of patient satisfaction makes it possible to identify problem areas in healthcare delivery in a timely manner and to develop evidence-based managerial decisions aimed at improving the quality of dental services.

Conclusions

1. The study demonstrated that the level of patient satisfaction with the quality of dental care in a private dental clinic in Shymkent is high, with a mean score of 8.7 ± 0.1 points on a 10-point scale. A high level of satisfaction (8–10 points) was observed in 76.7% of patients.

2. The highest satisfaction scores were observed for the parameters treatment quality and dentist attitude, indicating the leading role of medical staff professionalism and clinical treatment outcomes in the formation of positive evaluations of dental care.

3. The lowest satisfaction scores were identified for waiting time and appointment availability, indicating the presence of reserves for improving organizational aspects of healthcare delivery.

4. Patient satisfaction was shown to be an informative indicator of dental care quality and can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of healthcare organization performance.

5. Patient satisfaction analysis can be considered an effective management tool for healthcare organizations, allowing identification of problem areas in dental care delivery and development of measures aimed at improving the quality of medical services.

Thus, the results of the study demonstrated that patient satisfaction is an important integral indicator of dental care quality and the effectiveness of healthcare organization performance. The high level of patient satisfaction indicates an adequate level of organization of the diagnostic and treatment process in the studied dental clinic.

At the same time, the identified differences in the evaluation of individual quality parameters indicate the presence of organizational factors requiring improvement. The most important directions for improving the quality of dental care include optimization of the appointment scheduling process, reduction of patient waiting time, and improvement of patient information systems.

Regular patient satisfaction studies make it possible to monitor the quality of medical care and to develop scientifically grounded managerial decisions [20]. The use of patient survey results contributes to improving the performance of healthcare organizations and enhancing the quality of dental care provided to the population.

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